

Arkansas' Lithium Future: Impacts and Implications

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The views and opinions expressed in this chapter are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of any government agency or any other institution named herein. Errors and omissions are the responsibility of the authors alone.

Executive Summary

This report investigates the growing lithium extraction industry in South Arkansas. Arkansas is home to the Smackover Formation, a limestone reservoir that holds brine with high concentrations of lithium and bromine. While bromine has been extracted for decades from this formation, new demand for lithium ion batteries in electric vehicles has sparked interest in lithium extraction in the region. Large multinational companies such as ExxonMobil have made large investments in the region as they seek to domestically extract lithium. With such large investments come significant opportunities for socioeconomic development in South Arkansas.

We conducted a stakeholder assessment through site visits and interviews with key players, including local governments, new and existing industry, and chambers of commerce. Using qualitative data from these interviews, we analyzed the interest, influence, and ability to impact for each stakeholder groups across a variety of sectors, such as industry profits, inequality, and environmental protection. This analysis revealed the opportunities for socioeconomic improvement that have not yet occurred, and the players who might influence this sector. Overall, it demonstrated industry's large ability to impact socioeconomic development, and the ability for local governments to further leverage political power. Using our takeaways from these interactions, we also conducted analyses of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOTs) of the lithium industry's development. This analysis generally revealed a willingness for strategic partnerships, funding for lithium focused development, a large racial-economic divide, and a lack of coordination.

Finally, we developed policy recommendations across three sectors: Community Engagement and Civic Infrastructure, Workforce and Economic Development, and Environmental Impacts. Below are the high level recommendations we devised for each sector:

Community Engagement and Civic Infrastructure

- Convene critical stakeholders in the region through a sector partnership
- Convene appointed citizens in a citizens assembly to implement engagement strategies
- Convene philanthropic partners representing community and industry interest to support community development

Workforce and Economic Development

- Implement a sliding scale lithium royalty structure where the royalties for landowners are adjusted based on the price of lithium
- Strengthen educational programming to facilitate entry into the lithium and ancillary industries
- Apply to state and federal grants that aim to cultivate regional industries and strong workforces
- Develop a multi-county growth management strategy to identify infrastructural gaps and work to build a region that is ready for changes from a new industry

Environmental Impacts

- Implement rigorous monitoring and mitigation measures to safeguard local ecosystems and ensure sustainable water resource management
- Develop and implement a risk assessment checklist for the hydrological ecosystem
- Devise strict guidelines for the treatment and disposal or reinjection of post-extraction brine

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Introduction

Lithium is a pivotal component in modern battery technology. As the demand for lithium-ion batteries escalates, fueled by the surge in electric vehicles, mobile technologies, and renewable energy storage systems, the security of lithium supply chains has emerged as a critical economic and strategic issue [1]. The current global landscape of lithium supply is highly concentrated, with a significant portion of production dominated by a few players in the market. This concentration not only heightens geopolitical risks, but also poses supply security concerns for the United States' domestic battery manufacturing capabilities. Currently, a single country, China, controls more than 60% of the global supply of lithium-based precursors for battery materials [2] as shown in Figure 1.1. This dominance presents a substantial risk to the expansion of battery manufacturing. Resilience in terms of the lithium supply chain refers to the ability of countries to withstand and adapt to market volatilities, geopolitical tensions, and technological changes in the battery sector. Enhancing resilience involves diversifying supply sources [3].

Figure 1.1: Precursor Material Production for Lithium-ion Batteries: China dominates the production of most precursors for Lithium-ion Batteries presenting a huge risk of growing battery manufacturing across the globe [2]

As global demand for lithium escalates, Arkansas can help diversify the mineral supply chain. The state's unique geological resources, specifically the lithium-rich brine reserves in South Arkansas, position it as a pivotal player in this critical sector [4]. Arkansas' lithium potential builds a case for creating a more resilient supply of Lithium not only for the US but also for the world. These lithium reserves present an opportunity to mitigate supply chain risk for battery manufacturing for both domestic and international players.

The discovery and subsequent development of extensive lithium reserves in the brines of south Arkansas not only promise substantial economic benefits, but also pose unique challenges and responsibilities. This report provides background on the existing brine industry, identifies key stakeholders, and scrutinizes the environmental considerations associated with lithium extraction processes. By integrating data from industry experts, academic research, and community feedback, this report aims to furnish policymakers, industry leaders, and community stakeholders with insights and strategies to harness these opportunities responsibly. Through detailed stakeholder analysis and policy recommendations, the report delves into the potential for industrial and economic growth that balances economic aspirations with social equity and environmental sustainability for a diversified lithium supply chain, thereby shaping a prosperous and sustainable future for all.

Background Information

2.1. Brine in South Arkansas

South Arkansas holds substantial brine reserves with a high bromide and lithium concentration [4]. Unveiled in the midst of the 1921 oil boom, these reserves have since become instrumental to the chemical industry, particularly within the Smackover Limestone Formation—a geological wonder extending as deep as 1.5 km below the surface [5], [6]. The genesis of the Smackover Formation can be traced back to the ancient Gulf of Mexico, which once spanned the southern reaches of Arkansas as shown in Figure 2.1. As these primordial waters receded, a complex interplay of geological processes ensued, layering organic matter with saline water to eventually forge the prolific brine reservoir [7]. This formation's porosity is particularly advantageous, allowing for the efficient extraction of brine, which is then funneled through pipelines to processing plants [8].

Figure 2.1: The saline water of the Gulf of Mexico in the Upper Jurassic time extended into South Arkansas, which is why the Smackover Formation in Arkansas today, has substantial brine reserves Figure from [9].

The geological characteristics observed in the Smackover Formation are not unique to south Arkansas. Regions in east Texas and northern Louisiana, for instance, share a similar geological history and have shown signs of brine deposits with potential lithium concentrations [8]. However, while these areas share geological similarities, south Arkansas has capitalized on these features more effectively and has a more established industry utilizing the brine.

There has been a large bromine industry in the area for a few decades utilizing this brine for bromine extraction [10]. Bromine is separated from the brine using chlorine in a chemical reaction [11]. This bromine is then harnessed to manufacture a variety of brominated products, essential in several industrial applications [12]. Following extraction, the process is rounded off by returning the treated saltwater to its subterranean source, thus preserving the delicate ecological balance and ensuring the sustainability of this precious resource [13].

Given lithium's pivotal role in battery technology, essential for electric vehicles and energy storage, these brine reserves are more than just a bromine source—they represent a future source for lithium production. Amidst the growing global push towards green energy, south Arkansas's brine reserves

have caught the eye of the lithium industry [14]. The region's existing infrastructure, alongside its history and expertise in brine extraction and processing, positions south Arkansas as an emerging hub for lithium.

2.2. Existing Players in the Brine Industry

Companies like Albemarle and LANXESS have extracted bromine from south Arkansas for years [15]. LANXESS, one of the two big players, operates three plant sites in south Arkansas: Central, South, and West regions, with a focus on brine operations that underscores its core business activities around bromine [16]. The company's structure is bolstered by a dedicated Land Department, ensuring the meticulous management of its geographical assets and regulatory compliance [16].

Figure 2.2: LANXESS, is a company with a significant presence in the chemical manufacturing sector for bromine from brine. Figure from [16]

Integral to LANXESS's operational efficiency are its support functions, which encompass Environmental Health, Safety & Sustainability (EHS&S); Human Resources, Finance, Procurement, and Logistics. These departments form the backbone of the company, ensuring smooth operations and adherence to best practices in corporate governance and employee welfare. With a robust workforce of 440 employees, LANXESS stands as a major employer in the region. This manpower contributes to the company's distinction as the largest site in North America under the LANXESS banner [16].

2.3. Lithium Extraction in South Arkansas

Lithium deposits primarily occur in the form of lithium-rich brines found in underground aquifers and geothermal reservoirs in the area [4]. The unique geological conditions in south Arkansas have created favorable environments for the accumulation of lithium, making the region a potentially lucrative hub for lithium extraction. The existing bromine industry in Arkansas utilizing brine paves the way for setting up an industry utilizing brine to extract lithium. This ecosystem has attracted several industry players to the area like ExxonMobil and Standard Lithium as shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Several exploration and mining companies have expressed interest in tapping into Arkansas' lithium resources. Players like Standard Lithium and ExxonMobil have conducted feasibility studies and exploration activities in the region. These companies recognize the strategic importance of securing a domestic supply of lithium to meet the growing demand driven by the electric vehicle revolution.

Both Standard Lithium and ExxonMobil are looking toward Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE) for their lithium extraction activities [17], [18]. DLE is an innovative technology aimed at improving the efficiency of lithium extraction from brine sources [19]. This method is distinct from the traditional

solar evaporation ponds, utilizing various chemical, physical, or electrochemical techniques to selectively isolate lithium ions from brine [19]. DLE processes can extract lithium within hours, a stark contrast to traditional methods [4]. Environmental benefits also stand out as DLE technologies generally minimize landscape disruption because of their low areal footprint compared to evaporation ponds [20]. Moreover, DLE can produce high-purity lithium directly from the extraction phase, reducing the need for extensive refining [4].

Despite its advantages, DLE faces several challenges. The technology involved is complex and varied, requiring significant technical expertise to optimize [21]. The initial setup costs can also be prohibitive, with economic viability heavily dependent on the scale of operations and specific brine characteristics [21]. Energy consumption is another concern, especially for processes that involve extensive pumping and treatment—factors that impact the overall environmental footprint [22]. The water intensity of such projects can be varied, albeit less than evaporation ponds [23]. Regulatory hurdles and social acceptance are crucial, particularly in regions sensitive to environmental and water usage issues.

Standard Lithium has partnered with existing brine company LANXESS to utilize the tail brine from their bromine operations for their DLE process [24]. They have set up a demonstration plant at the LANXESS South plant and have achieved production of battery grade Lithium Carbonate and Lithium Hydroxide. However, they still remain a few years away from commercialization because of a lack of profitability [25].

ExxonMobil does not have operations in the region yet but is currently in the process of drilling for brine wells to investigate lithium concentration in various regions. They plan to begin operations by the year 2026 [26].

Stakeholder Analysis

3.1. Methodology for Analysis

We held both in-person and virtual conversations with various stakeholders. We conducted eighteen formal interviews, attended two public meetings, and held background interviews with many more stakeholders. We strove to engage a wide range of perspectives at the regional, state, and national levels.

For our analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis), we utilized audio recordings of interviews when interviewees consented to the recording. If no recording existed, we used written notes. Audio transcripts were obtained using Otter.ai AI Meeting Assistant software. From this transcript and interview notes, we created a table of key takeaways from each interview. This table categorized each takeaway by SWOT category and general topic, such as housing or environment. We collected over 250 takeaways, which we aggregated and refined to approximately 40 high level insights across all four SWOT categories. We then categorized each insight by its sector of analysis: Community Engagement and Civic Infrastructure, Workforce and Economic Development, or Environmental Impact.

For our stakeholder assessment, we used the same transcripts to understand the interest, influence, and impact of each stakeholder group. We defined these three characteristics as:

1. Interest: How interested are stakeholders in certain topics? How often did they bring up a topic, and how much emphasis did they place on it during discussion?
2. Influence: What power do they have to influence? Was this group characterized as influential in another conversation? Did they have robust connections to another group with power? Did they have the power, realized or not, to execute strategies and initiatives within the sector?
3. Impact: The result from multiplying each group's interest and influence scores.

We gave each group a 0-5 rating for Interest and Influence, and a 0-25 rating for Impact. We then visualized these ratings through radial bar charts for each stakeholder group, as seen in figures in Chapter 3.

3.2. Interest, Influence and Impact

In March-May 2024, we conducted interviews with a variety of stakeholders to gauge their interest in specific topics and to understand their interest in and influence over decisions in those areas. We examined seven key topics, as depicted in Figure 3.1. All interview responses represented in this report are anonymized.

We assigned scores from 0 to 5 to express stakeholder interest in each topic, based on the interviews, where 0 means the topic was deemed irrelevant by the stakeholder, and 5 indicates a high desire to engage in that particular subject. The results, illustrated in Figure 3.2, reveal a diverse range of interests among the stakeholders.

One notable finding, as highlighted in Figure 3.3, is the proactive community engagement by new companies yet to establish on-site operations in the region. These companies are keenly participating in community engagement efforts to establish a positive relationship with local communities well in advance of their operational setup. Similarly, city governments have shown a strong interest

Figure 3.1: Each stakeholder has a different level of interest and influence on the topics. We looked at seven topics as shown in the figure.

in housing strategies to accommodate the influx of workers expected with the burgeoning lithium industry.

We did a similar exercise for gauging levels of influence as shown in Figure 3.4. We also devised a score for "Ability to Impact" by using the scores for Interest and Influence as shown in Figure 3.5.

The topics that we probed included:

1. **Royalty Structure:** This refers to the financial agreements and payment structures established between lithium extraction companies, landowners, and government entities. Royalties are typically a percentage of the revenue or profit generated from the lithium extracted from the land. In Arkansas, the specifics of these agreements can significantly impact local economies and the distribution of economic benefits.
2. **Community Engagement:** This topic measures the willingness to involve local communities in the decision-making processes associated with lithium extraction. Effective community engagement can lead to better outcomes in terms of social license to operate and can mitigate potential conflicts. It includes consulting with local residents, addressing their concerns, and ensuring that the community benefits from the extraction activities.
3. **Housing:** The influx of workers and increased economic activity from lithium extraction can affect local housing markets. Issues might include increased demand for housing, rising rents, and potential displacement of existing residents. Ensuring adequate and affordable housing is crucial for sustainable development.
4. **Social Inequality:** Lithium extraction can have varied impacts on different social groups, potentially exacerbating existing inequalities. For example, certain demographics might benefit more from new job opportunities, while others might suffer.
5. **Environmental Protection:** The extraction of lithium may pose potential risks to the environment. These can include water pollution, habitat destruction, etc. Implementing robust environmental protection measures is essential to minimize these impacts and ensure sustainable resource management.
6. **Economic Development:** Lithium extraction can be a significant driver of economic development, particularly in regions rich in lithium resources like south Arkansas. This extraction can create jobs, stimulate local businesses, and generate tax revenues.
7. **Industry Profits:** This topic reflects the financial gains that companies obtain from lithium extraction. Profitable operations can attract further investment and technological advancements.

We interviewed a wide variety of stakeholders that included representatives from:

1. New Company: A business entity that has plans to enter the lithium extraction industry in south Arkansas, focused on establishing operational bases, forming local partnerships, and navigating state and local regulatory landscapes to build a sustainable market presence. Example: ExxonMobil
2. Existing Company: A corporation with established lithium extraction operations or demonstration sites in south Arkansas actively working to maintain or enhance its position. Example: Standard Lithium through LANXESS
3. City Government: The municipal governing body in south Arkansas cities located close to lithium extraction sites, responsible for local regulation, infrastructure support, and ensuring that lithium extraction projects align with the city's economic development plans and benefit the community. Example: City Councils of the City of Magnolia, and the City of El Dorado.
4. County Government: The administrative authority over a county that includes multiple cities and towns in south Arkansas, tasked with overseeing resource management, economic development, and environmental regulations at the county level. Example: County Judge of Lafayette County
5. City Level Commerce: City's Chamber of Commerce that supports local businesses and commercial organizations within south Arkansas cities that engage with or are affected by the lithium extraction industry, focusing on how this sector influences local economic growth and business opportunities. Example: Chamber of Commerce for El Dorado city.
6. State Commerce: The state-level department in Arkansas (State Chamber of Commerce) responsible for fostering economic growth, attracting investments, and enhancing the state's competitive edge in industries such as lithium extraction, ensuring statewide benefits from such industrial activities.
7. Local Residents: Individuals and families living in the areas of south Arkansas impacted by lithium extraction, whose quality of life, environmental conditions, and local economy may be directly affected by these industrial operations.
8. Environmental Groups: Advocacy organizations focused on environmental sustainability, specifically concerned with the impacts of lithium extraction on the natural landscapes, water resources, and biodiversity of south Arkansas.
10. Landowners: Owners of land in south Arkansas who may lease or sell their property for lithium extraction, interested in the financial returns in the form of royalties as well as the long-term environmental and property value implications of such agreements.
11. Educational Institutions: Universities and research institutes in south Arkansas that collaborate with the lithium extraction sector through research initiatives, curriculum development, and training programs tailored to meet the industry's needs while promoting sustainable practices. Example: Arkansas Tech University

When assessing interest, we found that new companies had high levels of interest in community engagement. In our discussions, they expressed commitments to engaging with communities to understand their needs many times. Communities in the area have an expectation of corporate engagement, since existing companies like Lanxess and Murphy Inc. have existing community engagement programs. This precedent increases new companies' interest.

In our conversations with city governments, they expressed high interest in housing. Lack of housing in the region is seen as a key barrier to economic growth. Without adequate housing stock, it will

Figure 3.2: Levels of Interest: Each stakeholder has a different level of interest across each of the 7 topics. We assigned a score between 0 and 5 to each stakeholder’s interest across these topics based on the conducted interviews, where 0 corresponds to "Topic was irrelevant to them" and 5 corresponds to "Wanted to discuss this topic the most."

Figure 3.3: What is surprising in interest? The new companies that have not set up their on-site business yet in the region through demonstration projects or otherwise were already quite plugged into community engagement in order to build a good rapport with the affected communities well in advance. It is also surprising to see that City Governments were highly keen on the topic of Housing for accommodating new workers who will be located in the area in anticipation of this new industry.

be difficult to attract and retain workers. While other infrastructure, such as roads and water, must be improved for population growth, governments expressed housing’s importance throughout conversations.

Looking at influence, we see that new and existing companies have a large amount of power. They have virtually all the power of stakeholders assessed to protect the environment, as they are responsible for environmental regulatory compliance. Further, their willingness to provide community benefits throughout the project is needed due to a lack of provisions for these benefits within regulatory structures. They have the power to influence housing and social inequality through these community benefits. Additionally, they have influence on royalty structure through their connections with state level commerce and the recommendations for these structures they put forth.

City and County governance do not have influence over the royalty structure, as the Arkansas Oil and Gas Commission (AOGC) devises this regulation at the state level. Similarly, environmental

Figure 3.4: Levels of Influence: Each stakeholder has a different level of influence across each of the 7 topics. We assigned a score between 0 and 5 to each stakeholder’s influence across these topics based on the conducted interviews where 0 corresponds to "Has no power to affect decisions" and 5 corresponded to "Has significant authority to affect decisions".

regulation is decided at the state level, limiting regional influence. Their main sector of influence is local economic and infrastructural development, since they can devise strategic programming.

Figure 3.5: Interest × Influence = Ability to Impact: We multiplied our Interest and Influence metrics to get an idea about which stakeholders can have the most impact on the topic moving forward.

Using our analysis, in Figures 3.6 and 3.5, we can see that the City Government has the highest impact on Housing, Community Engagement, Economic Development, and Social Inequality. Therefore, City Governments can be important agents in ensuring the sustainable development of a new lithium industry. Both new and existing companies in the lithium extraction business can have a high impact across most topics and have a huge role in shaping the lithium future in Arkansas. Existing companies can have the highest impact on Royalty Structure decisions to make sure landowners get a good share of the profits from resource extraction from their lands.

Figure 4.6 shows the highest impact levels for each sector of analysis. Greener colors indicate a higher level of impact. For clarity, only stakeholders with the highest levels of impact were included in this visualization. Intentionally, we did not allow our analysis to score any one stakeholder group with the maximum impact, since our stakeholder does not include all players. Some players not analyzed, such as state regulators, might have more impact, and placing analyzed stakeholders at maximum impact might mislead readers. Overall, one can see that city and county governments

Interest x Influence = Ability to **Impact**

Figure 3.6: Who can move the needle? Based on our calculated Impact metrics, we mapped the top stakeholders that can have the highest impact on each of the 7 topics.

and industry are frequently the groups with the most impact. Impacts on royalty structure overall are low, since the people with the most power are the state regulators, and regional stakeholders do not have the connections to influence at that level. Environmental groups only have real impact on environmental protection, since this where both their interest and influence primarily lie. Notably, new and existing companies have the same level of impact, due to their sheer ability to influence environmental protection.

3.3. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) Analysis

Our team also conducted an analysis of the interviews to determine strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) as represented by stakeholders. These findings are considered in our formulation of policy recommendations which are later described. Below is our SWOT analysis coded by topical areas that are highlighted in this report:

Figure 3.7: SWOT Analysis Key: Yellow for Civic Infrastructure, Blue for Workforce and Economic Development, Green for Environment

Strengths

- **There are strong public-private partnership examples** in both northwest and southwest Arkansas.
- **TA and capital resources are available** to support economic development both at the state and regional level.
- **Technical training programs** responding to new industry growth are being built and launched that **offer varying levels of attainment and certification outcomes**.
- **Industry players** have been **supportive of infrastructure improvement and economic development initiatives**.
- Arkansas has a **supportive policy framework for large businesses** and an **existing regulatory framework for extraction industries**.
- Southwest Arkansas has a geologic advantage compared to nearby state competitors by having **high concentrations of Li**.
- **Industry players** have a high incentive to take appropriate **precautions in managing environmental harm**.

Weaknesses

- **The region has been experiencing industry decline creating poor conditions for long-term public-private partnerships.**
- **There are growing trends in economic disparity in each county (Lafayette, Columbia, Union); this is particularly true when evaluating the racial wealth gap.**
- **Skilled workers are in low supply and difficult to retain** in southwest Arkansas.
- There is low educational attainment and poor retention of college graduates which has made it **difficult to recruit and retain skilled workers** in southwest Arkansas.
- Policy supporting favorable business environments are making it more difficult for cities to support community and economic development. There is **concern that communities will only receive marginal gains**.
- There is a **lack of analysis** detailing the public health, environmental, and utility impacts of new industry activity.

Figure 3.8: Regional strengths and weaknesses as uncovered from our interviews.

Opportunities

- **There are strategic partnership gaps that can be bridged to enable the flow of resources such as technical assistance providers** to support strategic planning initiatives.
- There are strong public private partnership networks in northwest Arkansas that can be **mirrored in southwest Arkansas**.
- There are federal funding opportunities that have **strong overlaps with state and regional priorities**.
- Business for local contractors is anticipated considering the influx of new high value contracts for infrastructure and plant development in southwest Arkansas.
- **Conversations to support more equitable economic development can be initiated** during planning phases of industry initiated support for economic development.
- Linking young-age adults and upskilling workers to **industry can be approached in planning for education and workforce development**.
- Conducting feasibility studies can inform key decisions made around sustainable development

Threats

- The southwest region is missing key civic infrastructure to support strong regional coordination which increases the risk of market failures when pursuing sustainable economic development.
- Local sentiments to uphold **partnership integrity conflict with public sentiments to be fairly invested in**.
- Jobs created for **extraction may not offer significant employment opportunities** if manufacturing is not explored.
- **Balancing in-state workforce development with out-of-state worker migration** makes community development and prioritizing funding challenging.
- Developing more wells in the region **may strain an already stressed environment**.
- Population increase without the infrastructure in place to support **may strain existing resources**.

Figure 3.9: Regional opportunities and threats as uncovered from our interviews.

Community Benefits Agreements

As we assess policy and make recommendations, one key overarching question is how to ensure that industry follows through on their commitments. One formal mode of achieving commitments is through community benefits agreements, which is discussed below. Arkansas does not currently have significant experience utilizing CBAs alongside major project investments. However, the complex conditions and potential commercial viability risks associated with the lithium industry necessitate potential solutions for mitigating investment risk for the private and public sector alike. CBAs are means by which communities can do that, and therefore this chapter provides a cursory exploration into CBAs for policymakers' consideration to enact the recommendations that follow in Chapter 5.

4.1. What are CBAs?

Community Benefit Agreements (CBAs) are legal agreements that facilitate cooperation between community groups and developers, ensuring community support for various projects [27]. These agreements often include commitments from developers such as hiring locally, contributing to economic trust funds, and providing workforce training. CBAs are beneficial for all parties involved—community groups, developers, and local and state governments. They enable developers to gain community and government backing, and can be essential for approvals like zoning, while reducing their project risks. Meanwhile, communities enjoy tangible benefits and improved project outcomes, making these agreements a collaborative tool for development [27].

4.2. Historical Evidence for CBAs in the Extraction Industry

The Good Neighbor Agreement (GNA) between Sibanye-Stillwater Mining Company, Northern Plains, and local community organizations serves as compelling evidence for the success of a CBA in fostering collaborative and responsible mineral development while safeguarding environmental and community interests [28].

The GNA, spanning over 20 years, has demonstrated its effectiveness in protecting natural landscapes, water quality, and rural communities while allowing for responsible mineral development [28]. This longevity indicates the durability and sustainability of the agreement, showcasing its ability to adapt to changing circumstances and challenges over time. The GNA operates through a collaborative, proactive, and precautionary process, emphasizing the importance of stakeholder engagement, trust-building, and transparency [28]. By bringing together local residents, mining company representatives, and community organizations, the agreement fosters a culture of dialogue, cooperation, and shared decision-making. This approach not only ensures that community concerns are addressed but also enables proactive problem-solving and the prevention of potential issues related to mining impacts.

Furthermore, key provisions within the GNA underscore its effectiveness in promoting environmental excellence, public safety, and community well-being. These provisions include citizen oversight of mining operations, the establishment of clear and enforceable water quality standards, access to critical information for local communities, traffic management plans to ensure public safety, and efforts to develop new technologies for environmental protection. Overall, the success of the GNA in Montana serves as compelling evidence for the efficacy of CBAs in balancing the interests of industry, communities, and the environment [28]. By fostering collaboration, transparency, and accountability, CBAs like the GNA have the potential to promote sustainable development, protect natural resources, and enhance the quality of life for affected communities.

4.3. CBA for the Lithium Extraction Industry in South Arkansas

CBA frameworks can ensure that the economic development opportunities arising from lithium extraction in the mining industry are accompanied by measures to promote equity, environmental sustainability, and community well-being. While the lithium industry presents significant potential for economic growth in the region, it is crucial to address the historical disinvestment and social disparities that have affected local communities. By establishing a CBA, policymakers can effectively address these concerns by prioritizing local employment and training opportunities to ensure that the economic benefits directly benefit the local workforce, in particular, historically marginalized communities. CBAs can help implement environmental protection measures to mitigate negative environmental impacts associated with lithium extraction and promote sustainable mining practices. CBAs can also enable investment in community development initiatives such as infrastructure upgrades, educational programs, and healthcare facilities to address social and economic disparities in the region and foster inclusive growth. They can establish mechanisms for revenue sharing and payment of royalties to ensure that local communities benefit from the economic gains generated by the industry.

Implementation of a comprehensive CBA framework is essential to ensure that the development of the lithium industry in south Arkansas is not only economically beneficial but also socially equitable and environmentally sustainable. The expansion of lithium mining in Arkansas has raised concerns among environmentalists and local communities regarding potential environmental impacts. Lithium extraction processes, such as brine pumping and chemical processing, can have adverse effects on water resources, ecosystems, and air quality if not properly managed. The development of the lithium industry in Arkansas presents both opportunities and challenges.

A CBA for lithium extraction in southwest Arkansas could have the following features:

Socio-economic Impact

- Establishing an appointed citizens assembly tasked with organizing and implementing deep engagement strategies, ensuring the representation of hard-to-reach community members in the strategic visioning process.
- Evaluating profit-sharing models on royalty structure and their socioeconomic effects

Workforce Development and Community Engagement

- Obtaining commitments to local training and local hiring
- Developing strategies for inclusive growth and community engagement with the explicit goal of reducing socioeconomic disparities across racial groups

Environmental Impact Assessment

- Implementing mandatory, regular water quality assessments for lithium extraction sites and hydrological risk management studies

The following chapters discuss all of these features in detail that can be used towards a CBA. In navigating the complex landscape of equitable economic growth and sustainable environmental management, it's important to synthesize multifaceted regional challenges into actionable policies. Addressing this imperative necessitates a comprehensive approach that encompasses not only economic considerations but also social and environmental dimensions. At the heart of this section lies a set of proposed policies aimed at fostering community engagement, nurturing a resilient

workforce, and advocating for sustainable environmental management. These policies are designed to empower local and state governments to take proactive measures in promoting inclusive growth and environmental stewardship. By integrating recommendations tailored to the unique needs and challenges of communities, these policies serve as a blueprint for fostering collaboration and innovation at both local and state levels, thereby laying the groundwork for a more equitable and sustainable future.

4.4. Limitations of CBAs

While powerful, CBAs require sustained and organized engagement from community groups to retain their power. Without engagement, CBAs could not adapt to the needs of residents, and may not be truly enforced. Before a CBA is planned and implemented, there must be robust civic infrastructure that enables citizens to engage in such agreements. In our discussions with local governments, many expressed a hesitancy to engage in CBAs due to the significant capacity required to build and maintain them.

Further, some local governments also expressed hesitancy in negotiating community benefits that were not also beneficial for industry. Without clear mutual benefits, these stakeholders saw formalized benefits as handouts. They valued companies as community partners, but thought binding agreements would oppose their values of self determination through hard work. Local government buy-in is an essential component of CBA formulation.

Community Engagement and Civic Infrastructure

The National Conference on Citizenship (NCoC) describes civic health as, “the way that communities are organized to define and address public problems” [29]. When organized well, communities generally have higher rates of employment, stronger educational systems, more positive health outcomes, and more responsive governments [30]. When disorganized, communities experience the inverse and a decrease in social resilience to poverty [30]. The integrity of civic health is increasingly being challenged in rural communities as governmental capacity is being strained by pressures from urban growth in nearby more densely populated cities. This urban-rural divide is posing significant challenges for rural communities and is no different for southwest Arkansas which competes for access to resources, economic opportunities, and infrastructure investment with regions like northwest Arkansas. One of the key consequences of this disconnect is the difficulty rural communities face in staying connected with each other and with the broader region. As communication infrastructure lags behind, rural residents may find it challenging to access essential services, connect with neighboring communities, or participate in regional decision-making processes. This lack of connectivity not only hampers economic development and social cohesion but also exacerbates existing disparities between urban and rural areas. However, innovative civic design and infrastructure presents an opportunity to address these challenges and strengthen connections within and between rural communities. Considerations for enhanced civic infrastructure might include exploring sector partnerships, deep engagement strategies at the local level, and convening private and philanthropic partners for increased investment in community development.

5.1. Sector Partnerships

Sector partnerships would strategically develop programs that serve communities and companies. This partnership can be led by the county governments and local economic development groups. Supplement these partnerships with a rural policy advisory bench to mediate technical conversations about regional growth.

- Sector partnerships would be across counties, and be a formal collaboration between industry, “community colleges, schools, labor, workforce agencies, community organizations, and other community stakeholders to **align training with the skills needed** for that industry to grow and compete [31].”
- Within sector partnerships, organizations engage in knowledge sharing around socioeconomic development programs, and can work together to strategically reduce racial inequality through programming. Sector partnerships can also intentionally include **community stakeholders that reflect the diversity of the region** and can identify gaps in programming.
- Within these partnerships, leaders can construct an advisory bench of industry professionals in order to better communicate complex technical information to various stakeholders. The sector partnership could consult this advisory bench with questions or research needs, and seek guidance on developing technically accurate and clear communication.

5.2. Convene a Citizens Assembly and Conduct Deep Engagement Strategies

To address the ongoing challenge of garnering civic engagement in city planning efforts in southwest Arkansas, it is recommended to solicit and allocate funding to build citizen coalitions and professional capacity to meaningfully support assessing needs in local communities.

- **In participating cities, this initiative should involve selecting a mayor- appointed, council-approved citizens assembly tasked with organizing and implementing deep engagement strategies, supporting the representation of hard-to-reach community members in the strategic visioning process.**
- **This initiative should also include long-term strategies to bolster administrative capacity, such as Hiring a Director of Civic Engagement.**

By adopting such an approach, cities can bolster their preparedness for regional economic development activity.

It is highly recommended to consider both near and long-term recommendations to improve civic health. In the near-term, it is recommended to convene a citizens assembly in participating cities who are tasked with conducting deep engagement activities. Activities might include focus groups, one-on-one interviews, community workshops, or other events designed to convene community members in meaningful ways; this will support local and regional efforts to improve public participation in planning efforts and build better understanding for local needs.

In the long-term, contingent on greater economic activity and larger municipal budgets, it is recommended for cities to hire a Director of Civic Engagement. An additional staff member to support administrative capacity in managing a more complex public relationship would greatly support community social resilience.

5.3. Convene Private and Philanthropic Investors

As the economic and political landscape of southwest Arkansas shifts to accommodate industrial development, so should our conceptions of public-private partnerships and their role in shaping public life. Key in this shift is considering the partnership of philanthropic organizations. These actors have the ability to leverage both capital and acute knowledge of local issues to make meaningful investments in community development that more comprehensively benefits the public.

Convening philanthropic partners with private entities to pursue community enriching investment opportunities has already occurred in southwest Arkansas, specifically in El Dorado. The South Arkansas Regional Hospital (SARH), a new non-profit corporation, in 2022 acquired the Medical Center of South Arkansas (MCSA) converting the regional health facility from a for-profit enterprise into a non-profit service provider [32]. SARH is an innovative partnership between the SHARE Foundation, MurphyUSA Charitable Foundation, Murphy Foundation, and the University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences (UAMS), each of whom represent separate sectors but are community stakeholders with commitments to public health and well-being in El Dorado. The outcome of this acquisition enables these community partners to better prioritize affordable healthcare in the region as well as support local ownership of critical community services.

Replicating this model is recommended in future community development endeavors, particularly in more population dense cities, such as county seats. Mobilizing Arkansas' philanthropic network

as well as interest by new private industry players to invest in local economic development should be considered in civic infrastructure building pursuits.

5.4. Considerations for Implementation

Deep Engagement Strategies: Implementation of exercises can be lengthy and require extensive planning which may not align with the current timeline strategic planning; exercise requires sufficient organizing capacity upfront and could burden government capacity.

Citizens Assembly: Elevation of decision-making power of community leaders could be met with public pushback; misalignments on establishing a governance structure could lead to decision-making gridlock or public dispute; maintaining a citizens assembly can be costly considering staff, meeting space, and administrative costs.

Hiring a Director of Civic Engagement: An additional staff member could represent an additional financial burden; could face resistance to change among existing administration or community stakeholders leading to skepticism in mayoral initiatives; could run into limited impact without significant institutional and regional buy-in.

Workforce and Economic Development Recommendations

6.1. Rural Economic Decline has Adverse Racial Outcomes

For the last few decades, rural communities across the US have experienced relentless economic decline [33]. Assessing median income, population change, and median age, unfavorable trends have consistently characterized rural economic health. This has been true for southwest Arkansas communities as well [34].

Concealed within narratives of rural economic decline are racial disparities largely described by disproportionate levels of poverty. In 2019, Rural Black or African American residents had the highest incidence of poverty at 30.7% compared with 20.4% for that demographic group in urban areas [35]. Similar trends can be found in cities in southwest Arkansas.

Up until 2020, El Dorado was the headquarters of Murphy Oil, a fortune 500 company. The company's partnership with the city over the last several decades has contributed to local wealth building opportunities, access to higher education with the El Dorado Promise, and recent public amenity contributions with the Murphy Arts District. However, today, El Dorado is racially and economically divided, burdened with workforce and education disparities across race, and is among the top 5 most dangerous cities for violent crime in Arkansas according to local sources. In the neighboring Lafayette County, Lewisville and its surrounding region have been working to address population decline, lack of housing, and lack of quality jobs [36]. These factors have contributed to Lafayette County having the 3rd highest poverty rate (23.2%) amongst all counties in the southwest region, the lowest median property value amongst neighboring counties (\$63,300), as well as the lowest median household income (MHI) amongst neighboring counties (\$29,882) [34], [37]; Lewisville's MHI is lower, reported at \$29,250 [37]. Notably, Lafayette County has the 3rd highest concentration of Black people in the SW Arkansas region (38.7%) [34], some of whom are concentrated in Lewisville whose Black population makes up the majority of the city.

These trends starkly mark a need to assess traditional concessions offered by industries generating economic activity and consider strategies that address racial equity in economic development. Without attention, the risk of reproducing patterns of exploitation is high, and downstream effects of community fragmentation and social inequality can follow.

6.2. Economic Development Metrics

Economic development organizations (EDOs) traditionally use metrics such as job creation and business investment to quantify their success. This method is increasingly seen as inadequate, especially in sectors like lithium extraction that promise long-term regional economic transformation rather than immediate results.

The current upheaval in the EDO landscape, highlighted by a marked decline in business attraction and expansion activities, is forcing a reevaluation of these performance standards. While EDOs aim to cultivate economic assets and enhance competitiveness, they remain shackled by outdated metrics that undervalue initiatives not conforming to the traditional criteria.

In the context of lithium, which is central to the renewable energy sector, an insistence on conventional metrics can obscure the strategic value of initiatives that offer significant future

economic benefits. Practices like inflating job creation figures or providing incentives for firm-reported data have cast doubt on the authenticity of EDO achievements.

To better align with the evolving economic landscape, EDOs involved in lithium extraction must embrace a new set of performance standards. These should reflect the initiative's long-term potential and strategic importance, offering a more holistic view of an EDO's impact on economic development beyond just immediate, quantifiable outcomes.

Across all programming for workforce development, developers should establish **accountability metrics**. When possible, these metrics are quantitative. Metrics should also define timelines for assessments. Further, EDOS should **develop the characteristics of quality jobs** for use within program design and assessment. Governments can use guidelines such as the Good Jobs Principles developed by the US Departments of Commerce and Labor. These principles emphasize the importance of stable and transparent pay, skills and career advancement, union availability, and fair recruitment processes, among others [38].

Chambers of Commerce and Economic Development groups should engage with commercializing companies to obtain commitments to local training and local hiring. Such commitments should contain quantitative metrics agreed upon by the local officials and the company. Within all workforce development, economic developers should make a commitment to target efforts in underserved communities within their jurisdiction. Specifically, efforts should contain an explicit goal to reduce socioeconomic disparities across racial groups. Such efforts could be quantified through explicit goals developed with lithium producers around hiring makeup or program participation.

6.3. Value-Add Economies: Battery and Lithium Product Manufacturing

Current industry interest is only in the extraction and production of battery grade lithium. However, this makes the region's economy highly susceptible to the price of and demand for lithium. To strengthen the growth of this region based on its rich lithium supply, state policymakers ought to devise strategic plans for bringing battery and lithium product manufacturing to Arkansas.

Other states, such as Nevada and Missouri, are doing work to develop manufacturing of the whole battery supply chain. This would provide further national supply chain resiliency, as well as regional economic resilience. Dips in battery grade lithium prices, for example, would not shock the region if value-add industries that rely on lithium were present.

Nevada has received funding both from the US Economic Development Administration through the Tech Hubs Grant and the National Science Foundation through its Engines Type-1 development award to build its battery supply chain. In a coalition led by the University of Nevada, Reno, the Carson City and Reno Metropolitan Statistical Areas have begun to build a tech hub focused on the whole supply chain for lithium batteries and other EV materials. This cluster will encompass extraction, processing, manufacturing, and recycling [39]. Like Arkansas, Nevada also has copious lithium reserves, and is formulating its regulatory structure for this new industry. The coalition working on development of this industry includes regional development authorities, economic development districts, private business, the utility provider, venture development entities, educational institutions, labor unions, local governments, and a mix of nonprofits.

Nevada's primary strategies are:

1. The establishment of Applied Research Centers at the Universities of Nevada Las Vegas and

- Reno to specifically innovate within lithium related technologies
2. State tax abatements that have invited 12 lithium related companies to Nevada
 3. Construction of a standing series of working groups that draw input from consortium members to develop strategies. One group of note is the Strategic Advisory Committee, which oversees the development and undertakings of the working group and sets strategic initiatives.
 4. Strategic collaboration between the EDA funded University Center for Economic Development and regional development authorities and economic development districts to address “community infrastructure issues [39].

Arkansas can look to Nevada’s plans to build out its battery and battery products industries as a strong example of incorporating value-add economies into this opportunity. Specifically, Nevada’s implementation of a Strategic Advisory Committee and the establishment of applied research centers would work well in Arkansas, where universities and non-profits have already expressed interest.

A long term goal for the creation of value-add industries in Arkansas is the application to the NSF Engines Development Awards program [40]. This program awards regional coalition awards planning grants for key technology areas as outlined in the 2022 CHIPS and Science Act, which includes energy.

6.4. Develop a Multi-County Growth Management Strategy

Faced with rapid industry development and new economic opportunities, regional coordination on how to accommodate and leverage new activity is needed in southwest Arkansas. Currently, there are critical infrastructure challenges, coordination gaps in workforce development and education strategies, and missing feasibility studies detailing the potential impact of additional users on utility systems; however, discussion at the county level regarding collaboration on these shared issues is minimal. Without regional coordination, southwest Arkansas may struggle to provide basic services to residents and meet resource demands of major industry players.

Developing a multi-county growth management strategy will support addressing these challenges and help facilitate inclusive and sustainable growth in the region. Key components might include strategies for improving infrastructure, the economy, community and quality of life, governance, and environmental stewardship. It might also offer recommendations for funding sources, implementation strategies, and timelines for completion. Producing a growth management strategy would clearly state regional priorities and opportunities for investment using either public or private funds. Key stakeholders organized through sector partnerships can produce this plan.

6.5. Educational Programming and Pipelines

Economic development agencies can expand apprenticeship programming in the region, both for lithium production as well as ancillary industries such as construction and electrical work. They can obtain commitments for extraction companies, when feasible, to work with the U.S. Department of Labor (U.S. DOL) and the Arkansas Office of Skills Development (OSD) to develop approved apprenticeship curriculums. When these curricula are developed with U.S. DOL and OSD, companies are eligible for a variety of funding [41]. Furthermore, the OSD’s Office of Apprenticeship (OA) oversees the implementation of registered apprenticeship programs (RAPs) that are approved on the federal level, as well as for setting the terms for certified pre-apprenticeship programs. There is therefore a potential opportunity to create an RAP/pre-apprenticeship pipeline in addition to, and distinct from, local hire policies. To strengthen local hiring, companies can also partner with nearby educational centers to develop pathways wherein students are supported in obtaining these apprenticeships.

To strengthen education pathways before college, coalitions should work with partners like SAU and regional school districts to establish more High School Career Centers. These counties are close to multiple universities, such as Southern Arkansas University in Magnolia, South Arkansas Community College in El Dorado, and University of Arkansas Hope-Texarkana. Developed under the Arkansas OSD, career centers allow high school students to earn college credit and develop useful industry skills at no cost while still in high school [42]. These programs are funded by individual school districts. Students can gain certificates in proficiency in fields such as welding, construction, and computer engineering. Within existing programs, through sector partnerships, educational centers can develop curriculums in construction technology, industrial operations, and other fields relevant to lithium development. Currently, SACC, UAHT, and SAU Tech in Camden are home to these career centers. Notably, Columbia County lacks such programming.

6.6. Grants and Planning Work

Industry and nonprofits, in collaboration with local government, should work to apply to OSD workforce development grants. Particular grant applications of interest are Skills Gap, Customized Technical, and Professional Development [43]. As discussed above, federal grants for regional development such as the NSF Engines Development Award are also opportunities for strategic planning.

Each county should conduct an assessment of existing infrastructure, specifically focusing on housing and transportation infrastructure. As suggested in the Magnolia Comprehensive Plan, they should explore the feasibility of community development corporations (CDCs) or community land trusts (CLTs) to develop affordable housing on vacant land [44]. Community land trusts would allow participating members to retain ownership of the land. Again, sector partnerships throughout the region would allow individual jurisdictions to share knowledge on organizational structures and creative solutions to common obstacles.

6.7. Lithium Extraction Royalty Structure for Arkansas

As Arkansas primes its regulatory landscape to accommodate the settling of major commercial lithium extraction players, there is growing concern for the fair and equitable distribution of profits reaped from a budding and potentially explosive lithium mining industry. Recently, the Arkansas Oil and Gas Commission (AOGC) has put a decision on hold to determine an appropriate royalty rate for landowners owning acreage in the LANXESS south brine unit [45]. The South Arkansas Minerals Association (SAMA), a group comprised of landowning beneficiaries, proposed a sliding scale royalty structure with a baseline 12.5% royalty rate [46], while Standard Lithium (SLI), a mining company with established project stakes, proposed a tiered royalty structure with an average 1.5% rate [46]. SAMA is concerned with fair compensation and securing economic benefits for landowners while SLI is arguing for a higher return on investment due to the burdens and risks of upfront costs associated with mineral processing, site development, and scaling operations [47].

The latest update with the decision is that SLI withdrew its application putting a pause on a decision to settle the lithium royalty rate [48]. Nevertheless, the challenge remains, and a decision to determine a fair rate is outstanding.

To address the complex royalty problem, it is recommended to establish a fair and transparent

royalty structure that considers the unique characteristics of the industry as well as the needs of various stakeholders including landowners, industry players, local communities, and the state.

This structure should involve adopting South Arkansas Mineral Association’s (SAMA) proposal to establish a sliding scale royalty model, ensuring that both landowners and companies receive equitable compensation while managing costs during initial phases.

The state can affirm the interest of SAMA’s proposal for a sliding royalty structure that establishes a higher base royalty with a real price adjustment rate. Pursuing a negotiation to confirm a base royalty rate is recommended.

This recommendation would establish a fairer and more equitable profit-sharing model based on lithium carbonate production, and satisfy SAMA’s protest and mitigate risk of collective action. This royalty structure improves the local economy by cultivating stronger wealth-building opportunities. If negotiated, it satisfies upfront lower royalty cost accommodating SLI intensive upfront costs.

6.8. Considerations for Implementation

Lithium Royalty Structure: Risks associated with securing a profitable project economy have been frequently cited by SLI and industry partners as the reason for proposing their royalty structure. These risks include shouldered costs for facility development and mineral processing, challenges with debt and equity financing, lithium price volatility, and immature market characteristics [49]. Stated by Tetra concerning these risks:

“Adopting a 12-and-a-half-percent royalty rate on gross proceeds instead can create the environment where lithium will continue to be sourced from other parts of the world to meet our nation’s new energy demands and leave Arkansas’ mineral and landowners on the sidelines [49].”

However, unlike industry partners just entering the Arkansas market, SLI has well established operations and partners for their Phase 1A project site. Confirmed by an SLI representative during the December AOGC hearing was that **the brine needed for processing is being produced by Lanxess**, a longstanding bromine extraction company, and being exchanged with SLI for a Brine Fee [46]. This existing infrastructure, as well as **completed technical studies, availability of brownfield sites in the region, and tax policy support from the state**²¹ **substantially derisks the Phase 1A project.** In other words, there is less risk and more value for SLI moving forward pending favorable prices for lithium.

Additionally this recommendation could instigate threats from industry players to divest interests or lobby for favorable outcomes, or potentially weaken Arkansas market prospects compared to bordering states. It may also be denounced given state interests to attract private industry.

Workforce Development: Opposition to diversity and inclusion practices might hinder targeted workforce development efforts. The view of **community benefits** and agreements formalizing them as **“unsustainable”** or as **“asking for handouts”** minimizes the leverage that communities have. As discussed above, Initiatives such as CLTs and CBAs require a **high level of citizen engagement and buy-in**, which can be difficult to maintain. **Further, capacity** to develop comprehensive grant applications and formal agreements **may be limited in small jurisdictions.**

Enhanced Environmental Regulations for Sustainable Lithium Extraction in Arkansas

Less than 1% of global lithium production currently occurs in the U.S. but there is potential to significantly increase due to abundant resources across a variety of landscapes [50]. Arkansas's lithium extraction is centered around the Smackover Formation, with operations proposing to utilize DLE—a method with a potentially smaller environmental footprint than traditional mining [50]. DLE involves extracting lithium directly from brine sources, bypassing the need for extensive mining operations. This method can potentially minimize ecological disturbances typically associated with conventional mining, such as habitat destruction and landscape alteration [50]. Additionally, DLE has the potential to yield higher-purity lithium, which is crucial for the production of advanced lithium-ion batteries used in electric vehicles and renewable energy storage systems.

However, DLE's implications for local water resources, including the risk of groundwater depletion and brine management challenges, necessitate comprehensive environmental oversight [51]. Moreover, managing the brine byproduct generated from DLE operations poses additional environmental concerns, such as the risk of contaminating groundwater and surface water bodies [51]. Current extraction proposals, such as those by Standard Lithium and ExxonMobil, highlight the industry's rapid growth potential which underscores that it is important to put systems in place beforehand to control any knock-on effects [52], [53].

To address these challenges, comprehensive environmental oversight and regulatory frameworks are essential. Rigorous monitoring and mitigation measures must be implemented to safeguard local ecosystems and ensure sustainable water resource management. Stakeholder engagement is also crucial to address community concerns and ensure transparency throughout the extraction process. We propose the following measures to establish some guardrails:

7.1. Developing Water Quality Monitoring and Reporting Mechanism

Implementing mandatory, regular water quality assessments for lithium extraction sites, focusing on salinity levels, heavy metal concentrations, and other contaminants would be essential. Public disclosure of water quality data to ensure transparency and community trust should be made mandatory to nearby communities. There is a need to establish water withdrawal limits for lithium extraction based on thorough hydrogeological assessments to prevent groundwater depletion.

7.2. Implement a Risk Assessment Checklist for Hydrological Ecosystem

The Desert Research Institute created a checklist for hydrological risk assessment for brine extraction in Nevada [54]. Arkansas could benefit from a similar checklist for every new potential site for brine well digging. TWe adapted the checklist in the context of Arkansas:

1. Are there perennial or intermittent springs or seeps within the Smackover Formation where lithium brine wells will be located?
2. Do geothermally heated springs or seeps within the Smackover Formation potentially impact the efficiency of lithium extraction processes?
3. Are there perennial or intermittent streams, rivers, lakes, or ponds within the vicinity of proposed lithium extraction sites near the brine well reinjection sites?

4. Is there a high potential for erosion and sedimentation within the Smackover Formation, particularly in areas where excavation and construction activities associated with lithium extraction are planned?
5. Will groundwater pumping for lithium extraction activities in the Smackover Formation impact the water supply of surface water features within the region, potentially leading to changes in flow regimes or water availability?
6. Are shallow freshwater aquifers, with the water table within 100 feet of the land surface, present beneath proposed lithium extraction facilities within the Smackover Formation?

If any of the answers to these checklist questions is yes, we propose that the brine well drilling project involved should go through a stringent risk mitigation plan developed and monitored by the Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Region 6 office that Arkansas is under the jurisdiction of. This checklist can ensure that there is adequate research and due diligence on water resource management. The answers to this checklist can be used to create a risk mitigation plan for this new and expanding industry.

7.3. Developing Brine Management Standards:

It is imperative to develop strict guidelines for the treatment and disposal or reinjection of post-extraction brine, ensuring it does not adversely affect water quality or ecosystems. The current guidelines in the area exist for the bromine industry but needs to be updated for the lithium industry.

7.4. Considerations for Implementation:

Development of recommendations for environmental impacts are limited due to the newness of the industry. Industry is still making decisions around how many wells they will drill to reach desired production levels. What's more, many DLE technologies are proprietary, and their exact environmental impacts are not known. These recommendations ought to be adapted as more information is revealed around these topics. For example, land use impacts depend on the number of wells drilled, and cannot be comprehensively studied until goals for development are known.

These recommendations may also depend on industry willingness to engage in increased monitoring and regulation. If the state does not increase regulations, then it will be up to communities and industry to reach formal agreements for further monitoring. These commitments would best be maintained through formal agreements by industry to monitor and minimize environmental impacts.

Future Work and Conclusion

Future research should include an analysis of the lithium industry's potential impacts and interactions with existing industries in the region. For example, timber production is a significant land use within south Arkansas [55]. Currently, the number of brine wells to be built for lithium extraction is unknown. Any analysis of its land use impacts for other extractive industries would be premature. However, as industry players further develop their plans, research on how this development will impact other significant industries is needed.

Future research should also focus on the relevant regulatory structures and legislation in Arkansas. While this research team worked to understand governmental stakeholders and their duties, we did not conduct a targeted analysis. Such analysis would strengthen continued work on targeted recommendations. Additionally, this analysis can include an understanding of political splits within agencies, and how their goals are shaped by their current leaders.

Further on-the-ground engagement and interviews should be conducted to refine the stakeholder assessment and SWOT analysis presented within this report. Specifically, researchers should focus on meeting with local residents and faith-based institutions in South Arkansas. Local residents could be engaged through both one-on-one interviews and group forums. Some of the analysis in our stakeholder assessment was based on one or two conversations. Overall, continued stakeholder engagement with careful qualitative analysis will allow for a more granular and complex understanding of values and needs.

Within continued conversations, we also recommend that researchers share the report with stakeholders to assess reactions. The report should be shared with those interviewed, and any input they have on the stakeholder assessment and SWOT analysis should be considered throughout future research. Work can be done with the existing client team and engaged teams on the ground to convene stakeholders around these recommendations and collect feedback. These feedback sessions should also include discussion about methods for effective implementation of recommendations.

The implementation of a Community Benefits Agreement (CBA) framework for lithium extraction in the mining industry in South Arkansas can ensure equitable and sustainable growth. By prioritizing local employment, implementing environmental protection measures, investing in community development initiatives, and establishing mechanisms for revenue sharing, policymakers can ensure that the benefits of lithium extraction are shared equitably among local communities. Moreover, the success of the Good Neighbor Agreement (GNA) in Montana serves as compelling evidence for the effectiveness of CBAs in fostering collaboration, transparency, and responsible mineral development while safeguarding environmental and community interests.

As Arkansas seeks to capitalize on its significant lithium deposits, collaborative efforts between industry stakeholders, government agencies, and local communities will be essential to strike a balance between economic development and environmental conservation. By adopting a holistic approach that integrates economic growth with social equity and environmental stewardship, Arkansas can pave the way for a sustainable and prosperous future for all stakeholders involved in the lithium industry.

This report addresses a critical element of the battery supply chain — lithium sourcing — by detailing the potential for lithium extraction from brine reserves in south Arkansas. This diversification is vital for the United States to reduce dependence on a few dominant suppliers and mitigate

geopolitical and supply risks. The Arkansas model exemplifies how local frameworks, adapted for regional specificity, can contribute to the resilience of the global supply chain. This approach not only enhances the supply chain's stability but also ensures that the economic benefits are widely distributed, supporting sustainable development.

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